

NEANIAS
**Novel EOSC services for Emerging Atmosphere,
Underwater and Space Challenges**

Deliverable

**Deliverable: D4.4 Report on the Developed and Validated Space
Thematic Services (Release #1)**

30/11/2020

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D4.4 Report on the Developed and Validated Space Thematic Services (Release #1)

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D4.4 Report on the Developed and Validated Space Thematic Services (Release #1)

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Disclaimer

NEANIAS is a Research and Innovation Action funded by European Union under Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme, via grant agreement No. 863448.

NEANIAS is project that comprehensively addresses the 'Prototyping New Innovative Services' challenge set out in the 'Roadmap for EOSC' foreseen actions. It drives the co-design, delivery, and integration into EOSC of innovative thematic services, derived from state-of-the-art research assets and practices in three major sectors: underwater research, atmospheric research and space research. In each sector it engages a diverse set of research and business groups, practices, and technologies and will not only address its community-specific needs but will also enable the transition of the respective community to the EOSC concept and Open Science principles. NEANIAS provides its communities with plentiful resource access, collaboration instruments, and interdisciplinary research mechanisms, which will amplify and broaden each community's research and knowledge generation activities. NEANIAS delivers a rich set of services, designed to be flexible and extensible, able to accommodate the needs of communities beyond their original definition and to adapt to neighboring cases, fostering reproducibility and re-usability. NEANIAS identifies promising, cutting-edge business cases across several user communities and lays out several concrete exploitation opportunities.

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Table of Contents

Document Info	2
Disclaimer	4
Table of Contents	5
Tables of Figures & Tables	7
Abstract	8
1. Introduction	9
1.1. Context	9
1.2. Content and rationale	9
1.3. Structure of the document.....	10
2. Release overview	11
2.1. Space Services overview.....	11
2.2. Release of the space services.....	12
2.3. Releases timeline.....	13
3. Space Thematic Services	16
3.1. S1 – FAIR Space Data Management and Visualisation (SPACE-VIS).....	16
3.1.1. <i>S1.1 ViaLactea Service</i>	16
3.1.2. <i>S1.2 Astra Data Navigator Service</i>	17
3.1.3. <i>S1.3 ADAM-Explorer Service</i>	17
3.2. S2 – Map Making and Mosaicking (SPACE-MOS).....	18
3.2.1. <i>S2.1 Astro Map Merging Service</i>	18
3.2.2. <i>S2.2 ISIS3 Service</i>	18
3.2.3. <i>S2.2 ASP Service</i>	19
3.2.4. <i>S2.3 ADAM-DPS Service</i>	19
3.3. S3 – Structure Detection with Machine Learning (SPACE-ML)	20
3.3.1. <i>S3.1 CAESAR Service</i>	20
3.3.2. <i>S3.2 Cutex and VLFF Service</i>	20
3.3.3. <i>S3.3 Machine Learning Service</i>	22
4. Space Services Validation and User Requirements fulfillments	23
4.1. S1 SPACE-VIS Validation and Addressed User Requirements.....	23
4.1.1. <i>ViaLactea Service</i>	23
4.1.2. <i>Astro Data Navigator Service</i>	24
4.1.3. <i>ADAM-Space Service</i>	25
4.2. S2 SPACE-MOS Validation and Addressed User Requirements	27
4.2.1. <i>Astro Map Merging Service</i>	27
4.2.2. <i>ADAM DPS Service</i>	27
4.3. S3 SPACE-ML Validation and Addressed User Requirements.....	28
4.3.1. <i>CAESAR and AstroML Service</i>	28

D4.4 Report on the Developed and Validated Space Thematic Services (Release #1)

4.3.2. CUTEX and VLFF Service.....	31
5. Summary and future steps.....	32
References.....	33
List of acronyms.....	34
Appendix 1.....	35
Appendix 2.....	37
NEANIAS <Service-name> <module-name> Validation.....	38

Tables of Figures & Tables

Document Figures

Figure 1: NEANIAS space thematic services delivery architecture and their integration with core services.....	12
Figure 2: NEANIAS Space portal screenshots.....	13
Figure 3: Space-VIS ViaLactea service screenshots.....	24
Figure 4: ADN user interface	25
Figure 5: ADAM-Space data visualization.....	26
Figure 6: CAESAR data and job monitoring.....	29
Figure 7: AstroML Jupyter Notebook hosted in the NEANIAS AI Gateway.....	30

Document Tables

Table 1 NEANIAS Space services released	14
Table 2 Software development plan of the Space thematic service releases including estimated dates for pre-releases, testing and production.....	15
Table 3 User Requirements addressed by the ViaLactea Service	24
Table 4 User Requirements addressed by AstroMapMerging Service	27
Table 5 User Requirements addressed by CAESAR and AstroML Service.....	30

Abstract

This document reports on the 1st release of the space services and the software underlying each service. This report, NEANIAS deliverable 4.4, comes out right after the first thematic space services release, deliverable D4.3.

The S1 Service “SPACE-VIS” provides an advanced operational solution for data management and visualization of astrophysics and planetary data adopting FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Re-usable) principles. The S2 Service “SPACE-MOS” makes high quality images from the raw data captured by instruments (map making) and for assembling those images into custom mosaics (mosaicking). Finally, the S3 Service “SPACE-ML” performs pattern and structure detection in astronomical surveys as well as in planetary surface composition, topography and morphometry.

For each *released* service a point-of-access is provided, as well as an *interface* which interacts with other services and *documentation* explaining how to use it. Documentation of all NEANIAS space services is organized under NEANIAS docs service at <https://docs.neanias.eu/en/latest/#space-services>.

Services reported here have gone through the first release round, most services have been integrated to NEANIAS authentication system service, the documentation workflow, and integrated with GARR infrastructure services and MEE0 cloud services. As expected, this first services milestone uncovered some gaps in the services deployment stack and integration with other core and delivery services will be addressed for the next milestones and releases.

1. Introduction

1.1. Context

The NEANIAS WP4 “Space Research Services” is focused on the co-design of three innovative services in the Space environment for user-communities for Research and Development (R&D). The space services will deliver a springboard of tools to enrich the workflows of a wide range of targeted users from academic/research institutions to industrial stakeholders, e.g. aerospace engineering and related technology companies, but also national space agencies and public outreach bodies, e.g. space museums and planetariums.

The first service, S1, named “SPACE-VIS”, provides required functionalities that enable efficient and scalable visual discovery, exposed through advanced interaction paradigms, such as the visual analytic, also exploiting virtual reality. Services belonging to S1 are being developed in Task T4.2 “S1 - FAIR Data Management and visualization for complex data and metadata service implementation” starting from TRL6 software modules such as the ViaLactea framework, Astra Data Navigator and the ADAM platform.

The second service, S2, named “SPACE-MOS” delivers multi-dimensional space maps through novel mosaicking techniques (i.e. stitching of multidimensional images/maps with overlapping fields of view) to a variety of prospective users/customers (e.g., mining & robotic engineers, mobile telecommunications, space scientists). Services belonging to S2 are being developed in Task T4.3 “S2- Map making and mosaicing for multidimensional images service implementation” starting from TRL6 software modules such as Montage, ISIS3, ASP and the ADAM Data Processing System.

Finally, the S3 service, named “SPACE-ML”, delivers structure detection capabilities addressing the researchers needs to identify and classify, in an efficient way, specific structures of interest. Services belonging to S3 are being developed in Task T4.4 “S3 - Structure detection on large map images with machine learning techniques service implementation” starting from TRL6 software modules such as CAESAR, CUTEX, VLFF and well-known machine learning and deep learning algorithms and methods.

Services and software development plan as well as the validation strategy are being guided by Task 4.1 “Space sector user requirements, service co-design and gap analysis” and outcomes of Deliverable D4.1 [1]. The Space Services testing and quality assessment is being performed within task T4.5 “Space sector testing & assessment”.

1.2. Content and rationale

This deliverable, D4.4, is a report containing the details of the developed and validated Space Research Services delivered in the 1st release listed in the deliverable D4.3 “Space Thematic Services Release #1” [2].

Preliminary documents have been prepared for each of the Space services (S1, S2, S3), within the NEANIAS WP4 workspace¹, collecting the required datasets for service validation, software underlying technologies as well as collecting all possible contributions as Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) to evaluate their success.

¹ NEANIAS WP4 Documentation (internal access only): https://citegr.sharepoint.com/:f:/r/teams/h2020-neanias/Shared%20Documents/WP04-Space/02_Services%20Requirements%20and%20Development?csf=1&web=1&e=Jhw16l

D4.4 Report on the Developed and Validated Space Thematic Services (Release #1)

The document reports, for each of the space service, the main release components as identified in WP7 for their delivery and assessment [5,6]; and their integration with core services provided by WP6 [3,4]. In particular, service *documentation* and service *interface(s)* exposing their functionalities in a customized way are reported and mainly provided by URLs. Furthermore, Service Validation as well as addressed User Requirements, identified and reported in D4.1, guiding the development are described.

NEANIAS Space services are built on top of TRL6 software – i.e software that is fully functional in their original domain – and evolve the software towards TRL8 – in our context, fully operational in a cloud environment. This first release aims at deploying the software in the context of the NEANIAS infrastructure, using cloud infrastructure and services provided by GARR and MEOO, and integrating relevant documentation, to be used as a test run for uncovering any major obstacles across the NEANIAS collaboration. In the first release a minimal set of selected features are functional and stable, and documentation is complete enough to cover them, thus rendering the service usable by end users.

In the next deliverables and milestones, as presented in Section 4.3 of D4.1 [1], services will go through complete cloud operation and stabilization procedures (TRL8).

1.3. Structure of the document

This document is organized as follows. In chapter 2, we present a general overview of the NEANIAS Space services, the release processes and tools, and a summary of the released Space services. Chapter 3 provides short descriptions of each Space service release until the date of writing this document. Chapter 4 reports the service validation focusing on fulfilling the user requirements prescribed. Finally, in Chapter 5 we conclude this report with a summary of achievements, discussing major issues discovered and outlining future steps to add service functionalities towards their eventual TRL8 evolution.

This document is part of a series of documents to be released during NEANIAS development as the services develop and go through major releases. Each release milestone will get a separate report like this one. Until the next scheduled release (expected in M23) this document may get updates, as often as needed, to reflect in a real-time way any major amendments and/or improvements within the NEANIAS space services

2. Release overview

2.1. Space Services overview

The NEANIAS Space Research services are aimed at supporting management and analysis of large data volumes in astrophysics and planetary sciences through **visualization** (S1 SPACE-VIS services), efficiently generating large multidimensional **maps** and **mosaics** (S2 SPACE-MOS services), and, finally, supporting mechanisms for automatic detection of structures within maps through **machine learning** (S3 SPACE-ML services).

The **SPACE-VIS** services provide an integrated operational solution for astrophysics and planetary data management aided by advanced visualization mechanisms, including visual analytics and virtual reality, and it is underpinned by FAIR principles.

- ✓ The **ViaLactea service** accesses astrophysical surveys to aid understanding of the star formation process of the Milky Way. ViaLactea Visual Analytics (VLVA) combine different types of visualization to perform analysis by exploring correlations managed in the ViaLactea Knowledge Base (VLKB). VLKB includes 2D and 3D (velocity cubes) surveys, numerical model outputs, point-like and diffuse object catalogues and allows for retrieval of all available datasets as well as cutouts on the positional and/or velocity axis.
- ✓ The **Astra Data Navigator (ADN)** is a virtual reality environment for visualizing large stellar catalogues. The first prototype has been customised to access cloud services for interactive data exploration and navigation with the ability of exploring advanced virtual reality mechanisms providing full immersion.
- ✓ Finally, the **ADAM-Space Service** (Advanced Geospatial Data Management platform) accesses a large variety of environmental data and is customised in NEANIAS to access planetary data.

The **SPACE-MOS** services provide tools for making high quality images from raw data (map making) and for assembling such images into custom mosaics (mosaicing).

- ✓ The **AstroMapMerging** service exploits Montage (<http://montage.ipac.caltech.edu/>) and is integrated with VLKB for merging adjacent datasets.
- ✓ The **ISIS3 and ASP** under **ADAM-DPS** service allows integration with data processing pipelines in ADAM which offers tools for planetary data analysis and for producing cartographic products, such as Digital Elevation Models (DEMs) and 3D models from stereo imagery.

The **SPACE-ML** services provide advanced solutions for pattern and structure detection in astronomical surveys as well as in planetary surface composition, topography and morphometry. The service integrates cutting-edge machine learning algorithms to perform automatic classification of compact and extended sky structures or planetary surfaces.

- ✓ **CAESAR service** allows to extract and parametrize compact and extended sources from astronomical radio interferometric maps. The processing pipeline consists of a series of distinct stages that can be run on multiple cores and processors.
- ✓ **AstroML service** has been developed to integrate a deep learning mechanism to significantly improve source identification, classification and characterization of sources in large-scale radio surveys.

2.2. Release of the space services

The first release of the NEANIAS space thematic services targets the NEANIAS ecosystem, currently realized on cloud infrastructures provided by GARR (<https://cloud.garr.it/>) and MEOO (<http://www.meeo.it/cloud/>). Thematic services are also integrated on top of core services provided by WP6 [3,4] enabling streamlined integration into EOSC. The main purpose is to deploy C3 services to support data analysis through artificial intelligence and deep learning as well as C4 services for data exploration and discovery in large data volumes through visualisation and virtual reality.

Figure 1 outlines the NEANIAS space thematic services delivery and their integration with core services for authentication and authorization, computational and data resources access, as well as C4 visualization and C3 AI services. In particular, they have been released as distributed systems, some (such as CAESAR) being directly accessible through REST-APIs on the GARR OpenStack (<https://cloud.garr.it/support/kb/openstack/>) instances tested on the GARR Kubernetes (<https://cloud.garr.it/support/kb/kubernetes/>) cluster for load scalability connecting to core AI Services.

Figure 1: NEANIAS space thematic services delivery architecture and their integration with core services

The NEANIAS space thematic services are reachable through the **NEANIAS space portal** (see Figure 2) available at <https://thematic.dev.neanias.eu/SPACE/>. The webpages of the NEANIAS Space portal have been designed for optimal community

D4.4 Report on the Developed and Validated Space Thematic Services (Release #1)

engagement with project outcomes for both specialist (e.g. astronomers and planetary scientists) and non-specialist target audiences. The webpages have been developed with HTML5, CSS and JavaScript and include the RSS feed from the NEANIAS Portal.

(a) Space Portal Home page.

(b) Blog & Articles page

(c) Space services navigation bar

Figure 2: NEANIAS Space portal screenshots

All documentation related to the Space services has been delivered on the NEANIAS documentation repository (<https://docs.neanias.eu/en/latest/#space-services>) and the relevant source code is handled by the NEANIAS GitLab repository (<https://gitlab.neanias.eu/>) eventually mirroring some repositories from the GitHub (<https://github.com/>).

2.3. Releases timeline

The Space Thematic services are released in three main cycles. Release #1 has been delivered in M12 (Deliverable D4.3 [2] and the relative report in this document). The following table summarizes the Space services released and the main information related to the release.

Table 1 NEANIAS Space services released

Short name	Sector ¹	Lead ²	TRL ³	Version ⁴	Core Integration ⁵	Documentation Status ⁶	Testing Status ⁷	EOSC Registration Status ⁸
ViaLactea	SPACE-VIS (S1)	INAF	TRL7	1.0.0	AAI, C4.1 VD – VisIVO	complete	in progress	yes
ADN	SPACE-VIS (S1)	ALTEC	TRL7	1.0.0	AAI, C4.3 – PMS	under-update	in progress	not currently
ADAM-SPACE	SPACE-VIS (S1)	JACOBS/ MEEO	TRL7	1.0.0	AAI, C4.4 – DS	under-update	in progress	not currently
AstroMapMerging	SPACE-MOS (S2)	INAF	TRL6	1.0.0	AAI, C4.1 VD – VisIVO	complete	in progress	In progress
ADAM-DPS	SPACE-MOS (S2)	MEEO/ JACOBS	TRL7	1.0.0	AAI, C4.4 – DS	under-update	in progress	not currently
CAESAR	SPACE-ML (S3)	INAF	TRL7	1.0.0	AAI	complete	in progress	yes
AstroML	SPACE-ML (S3)	INAF	TRL6	1.0.0	AAI, C3.1 - AI Gateway	complete	in progress	In progress

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Release #2 will be due in M23 (Deliverable D4.5 and relative report in Deliverable 4.6). Final Release #3 will be due in M30 (Deliverable D4.7 and relative report in Deliverable 4.8). The following table summarize the pre-release, testing and production project months and estimated exact dates.

		From project start			Exact dates		
Deliverable	Description	Production	Testing	Pre-release	Production	Testing	Pre-release
D4.3	Space Thematic Services Release #1	12	11	10	31/10/20	30/09/20	31/08/20
D4.5	Space Thematic Services Release #2	23	22	21	30/09/21	31/08/21	31/07/21
D4.7	Space Thematic Services Release #3	30	29	28	30/04/22	31/03/22	28/02/22

Table 2 Software development plan of the Space thematic service releases including estimated dates for pre-releases, testing and production.

Detailed plans for the 2nd release are reported in the next section for each Space service.

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3. Space Thematic Services

3.1. S1 – FAIR Space Data Management and Visualisation (SPACE-VIS)

The S1 SPACE-VIS services are tailored for Space Data Management and Visualization. The services provide an advanced operational solution for data management and visualization of astrophysics and planetary data underpinning FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Re-usable) principles and are based on widespread and popular tools like ViaLactea, ADN and ADAM.

S1 SPACE-VIS @ NEANIAS Space Portal:

<https://thematic.dev.neanias.eu/SPACE/space-vis.html>

S1 SPACE-VIS Documentation:

<https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/s1-service/en/latest/>

3.1.1. S1.1 ViaLactea Service

Short name	Lead partner	Contributors
VL	INAF	UoP

Service Status	The ViaLactea Service has been released as a distributed system including the ViaLactea Visual Analytic (VLVA) desktop application and the ViaLactea Knowledge Base (VLKB) data service. VLVA has been updated with latest UI and Visualization libraries and extended to work on Unix-based Operative Systems. VLKB has been deployed on the GARR Cloud Platform Service and has been integrated with the NEANIAS AAI for the access to the private data and to the Logging Service.
Service Endpoints	Documentation: https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/s1-service/en/latest/services/vialactea.html NEANIAS VLKB Instance: http://vlkb.dev.neanias.eu:8080 NEANIAS Service Catalogue: http://catalogue.neanias.eu/service/INAF.fair_data_management_and_visualization
Software information	VLVA Source Code: https://gitlab.neanias.eu/s1-service/vlva
Plans for 2nd release	MS4 (M14): First version showcasing Release #2 (M23): Integration with NEANIAS Data Sharing Service and, eventually, the Research Product Catalogue.

D4.4 Report on the Developed and Validated Space Thematic Services (Release #1)

3.1.2.S1.2 Astra Data Navigator Service

Short name	Lead partner	Contributors
ADN	ALTEC	UoP

Service Status	The ADN application has been released as client application for Windows and MacOS. ADN has been updated with functionalities regarding the aspects of time simulation, also through the integration of the core PMS service. Improvement of the UI. Update and improvement of graphic models. Reduction of resources used and performance improvement. Database integration.
Service Endpoints	Documentation: https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/s1-service/en/latest/services/adn.html Software download: https://github.com/NEANIAS-Space/ADN/releases
Software information	Source code not available.
Plans for 2nd release	MS4 (M14): First version showcasing.

3.1.3.S1.3 ADAM-Explorer Service

Short name	Lead partner	Contributors
ADAM	JacobsUni	MEE0

Service Status	Data visualization portal online, providing Mars/MRO/CTX footprints and reduced data products.
Service Endpoints	The service can be accessed at: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> https://explorer-space.adamplatform.eu/
Software information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> https://hub.docker.com/repository/docker/chbrandt/geoserver
Plans for 2nd release	MS4 (M14): First Version showcasing Release #2 (M23): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Integration of the NEANIAS accounting and logging services; Datasets portfolio <ul style="list-style-type: none"> continuous registration of datasets; registration of new datasets. Service evolution: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> integration with NEANIAS Data Sharing; investigation of Zenodo integration;

- Improvement of the UI

3.2. S2 – Map Making and Mosaicking (SPACE-MOS)

The S2 SPACE-MOS services provide functionalities for making high quality images from the raw data captured by instruments (map making) and for assembling those images into custom mosaics (mosaicking).

3.2.1. S2.1 Astro Map Merging Service

Short name	Lead partner	Contributors
Map-Merge	INAF	

Service Status	A Map Merging service using Montage is enabled on the ViaLactea Knowledge Base (VLKB). The VLKB includes 2D and 3D (velocity cubes) surveys, numerical model outputs, point-like and diffuse object catalogues and allows for retrieval of all the available datasets as well as cutouts on the positional and/or velocity axis and include merging capabilities on adjacent datasets. Additionally, another tool, named SCUTOUT, has been developed on top of Montage to extract cutouts from astronomical FITS images and, optionally, make them directly comparable for scientific purposes.
Service Endpoints	Documentation: https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/s2-service/en/latest/services/montage.html NEANIAS VLKB Merge Service: http://vlkb.dev.neanias.eu:8080/ SCUTOUT User Manual: https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/s2-service/en/latest/software/scutout.html
Software information	SCUTOUT Source Code: https://gitlab.neanias.eu/s2-service/scutout
Plans for 2nd release	MS4 (M14): First version showcasing Release #2 (M23): Integration with NEANIAS Accounting Service.

3.2.2. S2.2 ISIS3 Service

Short name	Lead partner	Contributors
ISIS3	JacobsUni	MEE0

Service Status	ISIS3 is offered as a Docker container. To render the Planetary data (by ISIS3 tools) as portable as possible, the `NPT` library was implemented to abstract the container when handling the data store/archive.
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D4.4 Report on the Developed and Validated Space Thematic Services (Release #1)

Service Endpoints	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://hub.docker.com/repository/docker/chbrandt/isis3 • https://github.com/chbrandt/npt
Software information	Docker `chbrandt/isis3:latest` (sha256:5c7302d7f412e21f83c5dc373ce151771aca238be89262843b0b251a63d080b7) uses ISIS version 3.9.1. NPT is currently at version 0.2.1.
Plans for 2nd release	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop context manager for NPT • Implement parallel processing on NPT • Implement thematic specific functionalities

3.2.3.S2.2 ASP Service

Short name	Lead partner	Contributors
ASP	JacobsUni	MEEO

Service Status	Docker container implemented
Service Endpoints	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://gitlab.neanias.eu/s2-service/docker-asp
Software information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NASA ASP suite, version 2.6.2
Plans for 2nd release	Integrate ASP in to NPT pipelines

3.2.4.S2.3 ADAM-DPS Service

Short name	Lead partner	Contributors
ADAM-DPS	MEEO	JacobsUni

Service Status	ADAM-DPS allows pipeline submission for pre-processing, ingestion and mosaicking capabilities via Kubernetes. It has been deployed in the MEEO cloud and it also provides a logging and accounting internal service.
Service Endpoints	https://explorer-space.adamplatform.eu/
Software information	The ADAM-DPS code is under proprietary license.
Plans for 2nd release	MS4 (M14): First Version showcasing Release #2 (M23): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improvement of the UI • New pipelines integration • Admin interface

3.3. S3 – Structure Detection with Machine Learning (SPACE-ML)

3.3.1. S3.1 CAESAR Service

Short name	Lead partner	Contributors
CAESAR	INAF	

Service Status	CAESAR is a tool for automated source finding in astronomical maps. It allows to extract and parametrize both compact and extended sources from astronomical radio interferometric maps. CAESAR has been extended to be used by REST-APIs and containers have been developed for Docker and Singularity. The CAESAR Service has been deployed on the GARR Cloud Platform Service, tested on the GARR Cloud Container Service, and it has been integrated with the NEANIAS AAI Service.
Service Endpoints	Documentation: https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/s3-service/en/latest/services/caesar.html NEANIAS CAESAR Service: https://caesar.dev.neanias.eu:8080/caesar/api/v1.0/app/sfinder/describe
Software information	CAESAR Source Code: https://github.com/SKA-INAF/caesar CAESAR REST-API: https://github.com/SKA-INAF/caesar-rest CAESAR Docker Container: https://github.com/SKA-INAF/caesar-docker CAESAR k8s deployment: https://github.com/lijlabs/CAESAR-kube-openmpi
Plans for 2nd release	MS4 (M14): First Version showcasing Release #2 (M23): Improvement of the UI, Integration with NEANIAS Data Sharing Service and, eventually, the Research Product Catalogue.

3.3.2. S3.2 Cutex and VLFF Service

Short name	Lead partner	Contributors
CUTEX	INAF	

Service Status	CuTex (Curvature Thresholding Extractor) is a photometric code designed to detect compact sources and extract their fluxes in maps with a complex and structured background like the ones derived from the IR/Submm observations. CuTex is developed as a package of IDL routines that are locally executed on a dedicated server. CuTex has been expanded by building a webservice with a public accessible I/O
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D4.4 Report on the Developed and Validated Space Thematic Services (Release #1)

	interface to process FITS files. The I/O interface is based on a persistent and interactive connection (websockets) to IDL licensed server.
Service Endpoints	<p>CuTeX webservice access (run on CuTeX version 1.1): http://ia2-vialactea.oats.inaf.it/ViaLactea-VSH/vshCuTeX.html</p> <p>CuTeX documentation: https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/s3-service/en/latest/services/cutex.html</p>
Software information	CuTEX is actually written in IDL The webservice works by processing the input data on a licensed server and it returns the outputs as downloadable files.
Plans for 2nd release	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Porting to an Open Source Language. • Deploy on cloud as a container. • Integration with NEANIAS accounting and logging services. • Integration with NEANIAS Data Sharing Service.

Short name	Lead partner	Contributors
VLFF	INAF	

	VLFF (ViaLactea Filament Finder) is a package designed for the automatic identification and extraction of extended filamentary features on astronomical images. VLFF is written in IDL language and its routines run on a dedicated server with IDL license. The VLFF routines are executed through a webservice with a public accessible I/O interface to process FITS files. The I/O interface is based on a persistent and interactive connection (websockets) to IDL licensed server.
Service Endpoints	<p>VLFF webservice access (run on VLFF version 1.04): http://ia2-vialactea.oats.inaf.it/ViaLactea-VSH/vshFF.html</p> <p>VLFF Documentation https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/s3-service/en/latest/services/cutex.html</p>
Software information	VLFF is actually written in IDL The webservice works by processing the input data on a licensed server and it returns the outputs as downloadable files.

D4.4 Report on the Developed and Validated Space Thematic Services (Release #1)

Plans for 2nd release

- Porting to an Open Source Language.
- Deploy on cloud as a container.
- Integration with NEANIAS accounting and logging services.
- Integration with NEANIAS Data Sharing Service.

3.3.3.S3.3 Machine Learning Service

Short name	Lead partner	Contributors
AstroML	INAF	UniMIB, SZTAKI, UoP

Service Status	The AstroML service has been developed to improve source identification, classification and characterization of sources in large-scale radio surveys. This release includes a deep convolutional neural network based on an instance segmentation framework (R-CNN) that allows both detection and classification of radio compact sources, radio galaxies with extended morphology and sidelobe imaging artefacts. It can work either as a standalone source finder, or as a classifier stage applied to source finders catalogue outputs of the CAESAR service.
Service Endpoints	Documentation: https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/s3-service/en/latest/services/ml.html NEANIAS AstroML Service: https://caesar.dev.neanias.eu:8080/caesar/api/v1.0/app/sfinder-nn/describe NEANIAS AstroML Jupyter Notebooks available from the C3.1 AI Gateway: http://90.147.190.27
Software information	AstroML Source Code: https://github.com/SKA-INAF/mrcnn
Plans for 2nd release	MS4 (M14): First Version showcasing Release #2 (M23): Improvement of the UI, Integration with NEANIAS Data Sharing Service and, eventually, the Research Product Catalogue.

4. Space Services Validation and User Requirements fulfillments

This chapter reports on the datasets used for the space services validation to assess service functionalities. Furthermore, the fulfilled user requirements by each of the services are summarized. Details on the Validation procedures and results of the validation for all the Space Services can be found in Appendix 1 and 2.

4.1. S1 SPACE-VIS Validation and Addressed User Requirements

4.1.1. ViaLactea Service

The ViaLactea Service has been validated using the following datasets from the public ViaLactea Knowledge Base:

DATASETS - ViaLactea					
id	Name of Dataset	Type	Source	FAIR	Size (GBs)
Astrophysics					
DS1-1	SGPS (HI)	Fits files (datacube)	Australian Telescope Compact Array + Parkes Single Dish	Y	4.4 GB
DS1-2	WISE (all-Bands)	Fits files (images)	Wide-field Infrared Survey Explorer (WISE)	Y	176 GB
DS1-3	CORNISH (5GHz)	Fits files (images)	Co-Ordinated Radio 'N' Infrared Survey for High-mass star formation	Y	84 GB
DS1-4	MIPSGAL (24 μ m)	Fits files (images)	Spitzer/MIPS Galactic Plane Survey	N	13 GB
DS1-5	Hi-GAL (all-bands)	Fits files (images)	Herschel infrared Galactic Plane Survey	Y	18 GB
DS1-6	FCRAO GRS	Fits files (datacube)	Boston University – FCRAO Galactic Ring Survey	N	11 GB
DS1-7	ThrUMMS (12CO 13CO C18O)	Fits files (datacube)	Three-mm Ultimate Mopra Milky Way Survey	N	35 GB
DS1-8	CGPS (HI)	Fits files (datacube)	Canadian Galactic Plane Survey	N	45 GB

D4.4 Report on the Developed and Validated Space Thematic Services (Release #1)

The following screenshots show some functionalities of the ViaLactea service and the ViaLactea Knowledge Base catalogues and datasets accessed through the ViaLactea Visual Analytics.

(a) Galactic Plane view for data access.

(b) Compact sources analysis.

(c) Comparison of data from different surveys 3d cube

Figure 3: Space-VIS ViaLactea service screenshots

During the validation the following requirements identified in D4.1 have been addressed:

Req#	Requirement	Requirement Type	NEANIAS ViaLactea Service
RA1	Increase multiwavelength studies	Storage	Deployed VLKB on the GARR Cloud Platform thus increasing storage and data access capabilities toward the integration into EOSC under FAIR principles
RA4	Improve portability	Cloud	VLKB Services available on Virtual Machine for easy portability on Cloud. VLVA ported on Unix-based platforms and updated with latest UI and Visualization libraries.
RA6	Improve Data Access	Storage/Cloud	VLKB data access is stable.
RA7	Improve integrability	Computing/Cloud	Improved VLKB access to be easier integrated into processing and analysis applications in complex scientific pipelines

Table 3 User Requirements addressed by the ViaLactea Service

4.1.2. Astro Data Navigator Service

ADN has been validated on the following datasets:

D4.4 Report on the Developed and Validated Space Thematic Services (Release #1)

id	Name of Dataset	Type	Source	FAIR	Size (GBs)
Astrophysics					
DS1-9	Hipparcos Catalogue	Plain text file	ESA Hipparcos Catalogue	N	Less than 15 MB
-	Hipparcos Catalogue	SQLite DB	ESA Hipparcos Catalogue	N	Less than 15 MB
-	Planets Catalogues	Plain text file	Custom Dataset	N	Less than 1 MB
-	Satellites Catalogues	Plain text file	Custom Dataset	N	Less than 1 MB
-	SolarStars Catalogues	Plain text file	Custom Dataset	N	Less than 1 MB
-	Subset GAIA Catalogues	PostgreSQL DB	ESA GAIA DR2 Catalogue	N	628 MB

The following screenshots show some functionalities of the ADN service and the datasets accessed through the application:

Figure 4: ADN user interface

4.1.3. ADAM-Space Service

The ADAM-Space service has been validated on the following datasets:

id	Name of Dataset	Type	Source	FAIR	Size (GBs)
Planetary					

D4.4 Report on the Developed and Validated Space Thematic Services (Release #1)

DS1-1	MRO/CTX/RDR_MOI	GeoTIFF	ADAM-DPS	Y	1 GB
DS1-2	MRO/CTX/RDR_PXX	GeoTIFF	ADAM-DPS	Y	740 GB
DS1-3	MRO/CTX/RDR_FXX	GeoTIFF	ADAM-DPS	Y	700 GB
DS1-4	MRO/CTX/RDR_GXX	GeoTIFF	ADAM-DPS	Y	900GB
DS1-5	MRO/CTX/RDR_TXX	GeoTIFF	ADAM-DPS	Y	22GB
DS1-6	MRO/CTX/RDR_JXX	GeoTIFF	ADAM-DPS	Y	150GB

During the validation the following requirements identified in D4.1 have been addressed:

Req#	Requirement	Requirement Type ¹⁹	Current solution Gaps Proposed improvement in NEANIAS
RP-5	To improve reproducibility	Computing	Open data and open software are crucial for results reproducibility, although it must be improved with auto-generated documentation.

The following screenshot shows some functionalities of the ADAM-Space service and the datasets accessed through the Explorer:

Figure 5: ADAM-Space data visualization

D4.4 Report on the Developed and Validated Space Thematic Services (Release #1)

4.2. S2 SPACE-MOS Validation and Addressed User Requirements

4.2.1. Astro Map Merging Service

VLKB-Merge validated on the following datasets:

id	Name of Dataset	Type	Source	FAIR	Size (GBs)
Astrophysics					
DS2-1	VLASS	Fits files	Very Large Array Telescope All-Sky Survey	Y	900 GB
DS2-2	GLIMPSE (8 μ)	Fits files	Spitzer Space Telescope	Y	32 GB
DS2-3	MOPRA DR3	Fits files	Mopra Southern Galactic Plane CO Survey	Y	240 GB
DS2-4	SGPS (continuum 1.4GHz)	Fits files	ATKA + PARKES	N	25 MB
DS2-5	WISE (11 μ , 22 μ)	Fits files	Wide-field Infrared Survey Explorer (WISE)	Y	88 GB

During the validation the following requirements identified in D4.1 have been addressed:

Req#	Requirement	Requirement Type ¹⁹	Current solution Gaps Proposed improvement in NEANIAS
RA1	Increase multiwavelength studies	Storage	Deployed VLKB-Merge on the GARR Cloud Platform thus increasing storage and data access capabilities toward the integration into EOSC under FAIR principles
RA2	Reduce images to the same technical features	Computing	SCUTOOUT developed on top of Montage to extract cutouts from astronomical FITS images and, optionally, make them directly comparable for scientific purposes.
RA4	Improve portability	Cloud	VLKB-Merge Services available on Virtual Machine for easy portability on Cloud.
RA7	Improve integrability	Computing/Cloud	Improved VLKB access to be easier integrated into processing and analysis applications in complex scientific pipelines

Table 4 User Requirements addressed by AstroMapMerging Service

4.2.2. ADAM DPS Service

Data reduction has been validated with the following datasets:

id	Name of Dataset	Type	Source	FAIR	Size (GBs)
Planetary					
DS1-1	MRO/CTX/EDR_MOI	PDS/ISIS3 image	PDS/ODE	N	0.5GB

D4.4 Report on the Developed and Validated Space Thematic Services (Release #1)

DS1-2	MRO/CTX/EDR_PXX	PDS/ISIS3 image	PDS/ODE	N	370GB
DS1-3	MRO/CTX/EDR_FXX	PDS/ISIS3 image	PDS/ODE	N	350GB
DS1-4	MRO/CTX/EDR_GXX	PDS/ISIS3 image	PDS/ODE	N	450GB
DS1-5	MRO/CTX/EDR_TXX	PDS/ISIS3 image	PDS/ODE	N	11GB
DS1-6	MRO/CTX/EDR_JXX	PDS/ISIS3 image	PDS/ODE	N	75GB

4.3. S3 SPACE-ML Validation and Addressed User Requirements

4.3.1. CAESAR and AstroML Service

The CAESAR and the AstroML Service have been validated on the following datasets:

id	Name of Dataset	Type	Source	FAIR	Size (GBs)
Astrophysics					
DS3-1	SCORPIO-BAND1 0.9GHz	IMAGE RADIO CONTINUUM fits file	ASKAP EMU EARLY SCIENCE (Private Data)	N	1.5 GB
DS3-2	SCORPIO-BAND2 1.2GHz	IMAGE RADIO CONTINUUM fits file	ASKAP EMU EARLY SCIENCE (Private Data)	N	1.5 GB
DS3-3	SCORPIO-BAND3 1.6GHz	IMAGE RADIO CONTINUUM fits file	ASKAP EMU EARLY SCIENCE (Private Data)	N	1.5 GB
DS3-4	SKA – SIMULATED BAND 1.4 GHz	IMAGE RADIO CONTINUUM fits + ascii files	SKA DATA CHALLENGE	Y	4.5 GB
DS3-5	Catalogues of point sources (such as WISE, 2MASS)	Ascii files to use as DL training sets	Vizir	Y	1 GB

The screenshots below show the CAESAR and AstroML services and some of their main features:

D4.4 Report on the Developed and Validated Space Thematic Services (Release #1)

(a) CAESAR website login page.

(b) CAESAR job submission form

(c) CAESAR file management view

Figure 6: CAESAR data and job monitoring

D4.4 Report on the Developed and Validated Space Thematic Services (Release #1)

Figure 7: AstroML Jupyter Notebook hosted in the NEANIAS AI Gateway

During the validation the following requirements identified in D4.1 have been addressed:

Req#	Requirement	Requirement Type ¹⁹	NEANIAS CAESAR & ASTROML Service
RA3	Improve source finding	Computing	CAESAR outcome improved with DL/ML algorithms
RA4	Improve portability	Cloud	Using both Singularity and Docker container technologies for the CAESAR service. Also it has been deployed on the GARR Cloud Platform on a dedicated Virtual Machine instance and tested on the GARR Container Platform.
RA5	Improve reproducibility	Cloud	Jupyter Notebooks employed from the C4 AI Gateway for easier reproducibility and accessibility to the software.
RA7	Improve integrability	Computing/Cloud	CAESAR and AstroML software exposed through REST-APIs and integrated to NEANIAS AAI adding capabilities to compose processing and analysis applications in complex scientific pipelines

Table 5 User Requirements addressed by CAESAR and AstroML Service

D4.4 Report on the Developed and Validated Space Thematic Services (Release #1)

4.3.2. CUTEX and VLFF Service

The CuTex Service have been validated on portion of images of the following datasets:

id	Name of Dataset	Type	Source	FAIR	Size (GBs)
Astrophysics					
DS3-1	MIPSGAL (24 μ m)	Fits files (images)	Spitzer/MIPS Galactic Plane Survey	N	13 GB
DS3-2	Hi-GAL (all-bands)	Fits files (images)	Herschel infrared Galactic Plane Survey	Y	18 GB

The VLFF Service have been validated on portion of images of the following datasets:

id	Name of Dataset	Type	Source	FAIR	Size (GBs)
Astrophysics					
DS3-1	Hi-GAL (all-bands)	Fits files (images)	Herschel infrared Galactic Plane Survey	Y	18 GB

During the validation of CuTex and VLFF the following requirements identified in D4.1 have been addressed:

Req#	Requirement	Requirement Type ¹⁹	NEANIAS CAESAR & ASTROML Service
RA3	Improve source finding	Computing	The ability to run CuTex and VLFF services to extract sources with different input parameters and threshold levels allows the user to identify highly-reliable sources, filtering artefacts and low-intensity objects.
RA4	Improve portability	Cloud	CuTex and VLFF services allow the execution of the two packages to everybody in the community without requiring a local machine with an IDL license.
RA5	Improve reproducibility	Cloud	The web services grant a quick and accessible way to access to high-quality scientific outputs and to easily reproduce already published analysis to every researcher in astrophysical community.

5. Summary and future steps

In this report we document the current status of NEANIAS space thematic services as of the first release milestone in the scope of NEANIAS/EOSC. Space Services are deployed either in the MEEO Cloud or in the GARR platform as a virtual machine in NEANIAS's OpenStack dedicated cloud resources, or as Docker containers through the NEANIAS Gitlab Container Registry instance. Services documentation are available through the NEANIAS Documentation infrastructure, all services have integrated some level of documentation. Testing of services is undergoing, the infrastructure for cloud tests, besides underlying software unit-tests, are under implementation.

A validation process was applied to check for service interfaces, authentication, documentation and the different aspects expected by humnas interactions. Exposed in Appendices 1 & 2, the summary of this process informa us that NEANIAS services must do better in (1) user interface, (2) documentation. On the other, the services have been stable and operating as expected as of this first release.

In the next period we will see Thematic services implementing automated tests, the integration with NEANIAS integrated monitoring tools, logging and accounting as for the KPIs established. Also, an important addition for the next phase is the implementation of products publication and integration to user spaces.

References

- [1] NEANIAS WP4 Collaboration, "D4.1: Space Research Services Report on requirements, Specifications & Software development Plan," NEANIAS, 2020.
- [2] NEANIAS WP4 Collaboration, "D4.3: Space Thematic Services Release #1," NEANIAS, 2020.
- [3] NEANIAS WP6 Collaboration, "D6.1: Core Services Architecture, Design Principles and Specifications," NEANIAS, 2020.
- [4] NEANIAS WP6 Collaboration, "D6.2: Core services Release #1," NEANIAS, 2020.
- [5] NEANIAS WP6 Collaboration, "D6.3: Core services software release report #1," NEANIAS, 2020.
- [6] NEANIAS WP7 Collaboration, "D7.2: Software delivery infrastructure and tools," NEANIAS, 2020.
- [7] NEANIAS WP7 Collaboration, "D7.3: Software Assessment Methodology," NEANIAS, 2020.

List of acronyms

Acronym	Description
ADAM	Advanced geospatial Data Management platform
ADN	Astra Data Navigator
CAESAR	Compact And Extended Source Automated Recognition
CRISM	Compact Reconnaissance Imaging Spectrometer for Mars
DL	Deep Learning
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EPN-TAP	EuroPlanet - Table Access Protocol
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
FITS	Flexible Image Transport System
IVOA	International Virtual Observatory Alliance
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
ML	Machine Learning
MRO	Mars Reconnaissance Orbiter
OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium
OS	Operating System
SKA	Square Kilometer Array
TAP	Table Access Protocol
VLFF	ViaLactea Filament Finder
VLKB	ViaLactea Knowledge Base
VLVA	ViaLactea Visual Analytics
WCS	Web Coverage Service
WFS	Web Features Service
WMS	Web Map Service
WPS	Web Processing Service

Appendix 1

The following table summarizes the information on the validation of the Space Services including: the number of end users validating the service, their category (Student/Academic/Research/SMEs), their affiliation (from internal members of NEANIAS or external partners such as University of Catania – UNICT, University of Malta – UoM, and Politecnico di Torino - POLITO) and their overall feedback.

Space Service	Number of Users	Category	Affiliation	Overall Feedback
ViaLactea	10	Students/ Research/ Academic	UoP, INAF, NKUA, UNICT (external), UNIMIB	90% PASSED 10% FAILED
ADN	10	Students/ Research/ Academic	UoP, INAF, ALTEC, UNIMIB, POLITO(external)	100% PASSED
ADAM-Space	10	Research/ Academic/ Students	INAF,ALTEC, UNIMIB, UoP, NKUA, JACOBS (external)	88% PASSED 12% FAILED
CAESAR	10	Research/ Academic	INAF, NKUA, UNIMIB, UoP	85% PASSED 15% FAILED
AstroML	10	Students/ Research/ Academic	UoP, UNICT (external), JACOBS, NKUA, UNIMIB, UoM (external), INAF	93% PASSED 7% FAILED

ViaLactea: The failed Use Cases related to the ViaLactea Service validation are mainly due to the installation of the VLVA desktop application that is not available for all Operating Systems.

ADN: Only one step in a Use Case is considered to have failed related to the ADN Service validation. The validator stated that he was unsure of what to do. Note: Some validators have reported permissions problems in running the application.

ADAM-Space: The failed Use Cases related to the ADAM-Space Service depend on issues linked to the graphic user interface portability (browser and resolution).

CAESAR: The failed Use Cases related to CAESAR are derived from a known issue of the *mozilla-django-oidc* library used for authentication. Currently the library does not implement automatic refreshment of the access token (there is a commit addressing that pending to be merged in the official repository). For that reason, when the user session exceeds a certain

D4.4 Report on the Developed and Validated Space Thematic Services (Release #1)

duration, the access token used to query the CAESAR API expires and the requests are invalid. As a result, tables stop loading. A workaround is to log out/log in again to get a new (valid) token.

AstroML: The failed Use Cases related to the AstroML Service are related either to some resource issues related to the AI Gateway Service or to indistinct validation steps (for users not used to JupyterHub technology).

All the validation procedures for each service and the results of the validation by end users have been collected and are stored on the NEANIAS Documentation Repository² in the WP4 area.

²NEANIAS Documentation Repository: https://citegr.sharepoint.com/:f/r/teams/h2020-neanias/Shared%20Documents/WP04-Space/08_Testing_Assessment?csf=1&web=1&e=NDS9ts (for internal use only)

Appendix 2

The validation procedures have been prepared for the Space Services following this template:

NEANIAS <Service-name> <module-name> Validation

Project Name:	NEANIAS <SERVICE-NAME>	Validation Designed by:	<Author of procedures> <mail address>
Module Name:	<MODULE-NAME>	Designed date:	<Date>
Release Version:	<MODULE-VERSION>	Validation Executed by:	<Validator name>
Dependencies:	<LIST-DEPENDENCIES>	Date of Execution:	<Date>
Requirements	<Requirements for all use cases>		
Service access/download	<Link to service or link to download the tool>		

Use Case#	UC-XXXX-XXX-XXXX-NNNN		
Description	<Description of the use case>		
Preconditions	<Precondition for use case, e.g., previous use case complete>		
Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes
1 <Description first step>	<Description of step result>	Pass/Fail	
2 <Description second step>	...		
...	...		
Use Case result			

Use Case#	UC-XXXX-XXX-XXXX-NNNN		
Description	<Description of the use case>		
Preconditions	<Precondition for use case, e.g., previous use cases complete>		
Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes
1 <Description first step>	<Description of step result>	Pass/Fail	
2 <Description second step>	...		
...	...		
Use Case result			

“Actual outcome”, “notes” and “use case result” are compiled by the validator.